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TEACHERS' PROFESSIONALISM EFFECTIVENESS AT VHS IN EAST BEKASI

E. Handayani Tyas ^{*1}

^{*1} Mandarin Education Department, Faculty of Education and Teacher Training
Universitas Kristen Indonesia, Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract

This study is focused on the teachers' professionalism effectiveness, it was done to find out how the teachers' professionalism effectiveness at Vocational High School in East Bekasi. This study was conducted at East Bekasi in some private schools. The method of the study was qualitative with a descriptive design. The subjects of the research were the school headmasters, vice school headmasters, teachers, and Teacher Organization (TO). The instruments of this study are observation sheet and interview guidance. The data of the study were analyzed descriptively through the process of data reduction, data display, and concluding. The result of the study shows that the teachers' ability improvement programs were done based on the teachers' need every year, the teachers' ability improvement program was done in and out of the school, there are some obstacles which are faced by schools in improving the teachers' professionalism. So, it is concluded that the teachers' professionalism program needs improving, and it should be goal-oriented. Besides, the obstacles which are faced by the school should be well overcome.

Keywords: Teachers; Effectiveness; Professionalism; Vocational High School.

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1. Introduction

As a basic strategy, education is carried out consciously and planned in developing all potential learners. Education educates the life of the nation. Through education, the human character can be formed so that it contributes to the progress and development of the nation's character building. Human resources are people who are ready and able to carry out the tasks assigned to them so that they can contribute to the development of the nation. To create quality human resources, intelligent, skilled, creative, innovative, virtuous, responsible and to prevent unemployment from rising, the government is working on it through vocational high school. The government plans to increase vocational high school. This program aims to produce high-quality workforce so that students who do not continue their education can take part in the world of work. Through vocational high schools, students are provided with work skills through vocational practical

activities - productive subjects, while general knowledge is obtained through several general subjects - adaptive and normative subjects.

Besides, the school seeks to organize fieldwork practices carried out in collaboration with industries or companies that are relevant to the majors studied by each student. So a student who graduated from a vocational school will have two diplomas, namely a certificate of graduation from a vocational school as provided in other public high schools and a certificate of competency testing from the industry or company where they carry out fieldwork practices. A question that arises and becomes a dilemma for students who graduate and the government is, whether the provision of knowledge through practical activities provided at the vocational school already meets the standards set by the business world and the industrial world and can graduates create jobs with the provision of work skills gained while studying at vocational school? The answer is not yet. This is caused by various factors that hinder the implementation of education in vocational high school East Bekasi. Therefore, to obtain high-quality vocational graduates, influenced by various factors that are sometimes difficult to predict. One of the factors that predominantly influenced the success of vocational high schools in producing quality graduates was the teacher. A teacher must have competence such as pedagogic, personal, professional and social competence.

The four competencies are the main capital for teachers to be able to take part as professional teachers. Therefore, the teacher must improve his ability to teach. With these efforts, teachers are expected to be able to develop a higher quality learning process, both in the mastery of knowledge, skills and have a good personality [1]. However, empirical data shows that generally the professional abilities of vocational teachers in East Bekasi Regency are still classified as moderate because the mastery of learning materials they teach is still low. As we know that the vocational high school curriculum develops according to the demands of the times, while teachers are apathetic. To overcome this problem, increasing the professional abilities of teachers must be a top priority in efforts to improve the quality of graduates in vocational schools. This encourages authors to research improvement professional skills of vocational teachers in East Bekasi.

2. Literature Review

The effectiveness starts from the word "effective" and the basic word is "effect" which means the effect, effect, success according to plan. Effectiveness is the desired effect of an activity or job. Effective is "The existence of effects (affect, effect, impression), effective, efficacious, can bring results, effective (effort, action)". So, effectiveness is a measurement of achieving the expected goals and objectives. Indicators of Effectiveness Indicators are components that become a measure to determine the effectiveness of an activity. The education indicators are a) Input Indicators; b) Process Indicator; c) Output Indicators; and d) Outcome Indicator [2].

The development comes from the English "Development." Development is a process, way, the act of developing". Development is an effort to expand, bringing a situation towards a completer and more complex. Development is more aimed at increasing technical knowledge and skills in implementing learning. Personnel development is an effort to improve the technical, theoretical, conceptual, and moral abilities of personnel following work needs through education and training [3]. Education enhances technical, theoretical, conceptual, and moral personnel skills, while training aims to improve the technical skills of carrying out work. The development aims to

improve the ability of teachers that are tailored to the needs of teachers themselves, through training and education activities. Processes and Types of Personnel Development Teacher ability development are carried out to improve teacher work productivity, increase teacher conceptual understanding. Through personnel development, school organizations can increase continuity and the greater sense of connection between personnel and their place of duty. Development is a key factor in maintaining personnel quality. Staff development can be carried out in the industrial world has four kinds of methods namely: training in the workplace; vestibule school; apprenticeship; Special education [4]. Competence refers to the ability to carry out something obtained from education, which requires good knowledge, skills and personality. Competence is a set of knowledge, skills and behaviours that must be possessed, internalized, and mastered by the teacher or lecturer in carrying out professional duties". Teachers as agents of learning at all types and levels of education are required to have pedagogical competence, personal competence, professional competence, and social competence.

The four competencies must be obtained through professional education; a) pedagogical competence - is the ability to manage to learn including understanding insight/educational foundation; understanding of students; curriculum/syllabus development; implementing educational and dialogical learning; learning design; evaluation of learning outcomes; and the development of students to actualize the various potentials they have; b) personality competencies - is a number of competencies related to personal abilities with all the characteristics that support the implementation of teacher duties. Personality competence is a personality ability that is steady, stable, mature, wise, authoritative, disciplined, wise, having good character, being a role model for students and the community, evaluating one's performance and developing oneself in a sustainable manner; c) professional competence - It is the ability to master extensive and in-depth learning material that makes it possible to guide students to meet the competency standards set in the National Education Standard. This competency must be possessed by the teacher in planning and implementing learning, and d) social competence - is the ability of teachers to adjust to the demands of work and the environment around the school [5]. What is meant by social competence is the ability of teachers as part of the community to communicate and interact effectively with students, fellow educators, education personnel, parents of participants students, and the surrounding community [6;7].

Teachers through educational supervision are guidance given to school personnel so that they can improve their abilities. Supervision is not to look for mistakes, but to improve and develop the capabilities of the teacher. Supervision is an effort to stimulate, coordinate, and guide the continuous growth of school teachers, both individually and collectively [8]. The main function of supervision is to improve teaching. Whereas the core objectives of supervision are: to understand the characteristics and abilities of individual students in the learning process; create an atmosphere that encourages students to actively learn on their own; and make learning activities in schools dynamic and creative, and have meaning for human life, Burhanuddin [9].

To achieve a good quality of teaching and learning, supervision forms need to be planned later, one of which is through educational supervision. Educational supervision can be defined as the process of providing supervisory assistance services to teachers to improve their ability to carry out the tasks of managing the learning process effectively. Educational supervision is assistance given to education personnel to develop better education processes and efforts to improve the

quality of education. Educational supervision aims to develop better teaching and learning situations. Targets of educational supervision: a) develop curricula that are being implemented in schools; b) improve teaching and learning process in schools, and c) developing all staff in the school ". Teachers Through teacher organization an organization forum is a place for the professional activities of teachers of similar subjects aimed at discussing various problems related to the teaching and learning process. teacher organization aims to improve competence, discuss problems encountered and find ways of solving them in carrying out tasks, provide opportunities for teachers to share information and experience, and build good cooperation with all parties to improve the quality of graduates [10].

Training Activities Training is one of the processes of preparing teachers for a job, helping to improve performance, and developing their full potential. Exercise is more about applying knowledge than mastering knowledge. Exercise is the process of change aimed at forming the expected behaviour. The training system usually includes training outside the workplace (off-job) and at work (on-job). Teacher training is distinguished into two forms: a) training through pre-service education/training is held at formal educational institutions; b). training through education while working conducted in two kinds of forms, namely: On-job training (training during work) is carried out in the relevant workplace, and Off-job training which is carried out outside the workplace [11]. Strategies for teacher professional quality development can be done in two ways, namely education on job training and education outside the job [12]. For the implementation of training, problems should be identified and determine what programs will be used, formulate objectives, design learning materials and media, design methods and media, establish assessment instruments to measure program success, allocate budgets, and determine follow-up programs. Furthermore, it should be noted also the following factors, namely: "Teachers to be developed, the ability of teachers to be developed, and the condition of institutions, such as funds, facilities, and people who can be involved as implementers"[13;14]. These factors are basic considerations that must be considered so that the program to be run later can provide effective results.

3. Research Methods

Research using descriptive methods with a qualitative approach [15;16]. The research locations were at vocational high schools at East Bekasi. The study was conducted for three months. The subjects of the research were the school headmasters, vice school headmasters, teachers, and Teacher Organization (TO). The instruments of this study are observation sheet and interview guidance. The data of the study were analyzed descriptively through the process of data reduction, data display, and concluding [17;18].

4. Discussion Result

Based on the results of the study it can be concluded that the school has tried to improve the professional abilities of teachers by doing a special program for improving teacher ability. The program is structured by involving principals, vice-principals, heads of departments/study programs, supervisors, teacher organization, and senior teachers. The program contains the development of teacher competencies that are carried out at school and outside schools, such as supervision, training, upgrading, training, teacher apprenticeships, seminars, and other activities needed by teachers.

Teacher capacity building programs are implemented to provide assistance and improve teacher work in improving teaching quality to be more effective. Suhardan (2010: 182) explains that "Assistance can be given in the form of advice and advice, showing resources, providing time, asking for help from fellow teachers, visiting classes, providing facilities, giving permission to participate in academic activities outside". Teacher professional development program is compiled because in vocational high school teachers need adequate skills in teaching. Through development activities, teachers can realize the importance of increasing their ability to be able to adjust their competencies with the advancement of the world of education, especially vocational high school Suhardan (2010: 191) stating that "Teacher development must be done when the teacher is in good condition which is very possible to do development that is when the teacher is in need and fully awareness". So, development cannot be done at any time according to the wishes of the supervisor, but the supervisor must be able to read the right time.

Teacher Professional Based on the results of the study it can be concluded that the school has implemented a teacher development program both within the school environment and outside the school environment. Implementation in the school environment is carried out in the form of teacher development in theory and practice. In theory, it will take the form of seminar activities, the formation and activation of the teacher organization and other activities. Whereas practicum has been done in the form of supervision and training, such as computer training. The teacher development program outside the school environment is carried out with teacher apprenticeship activities, sending teachers to attend training if there is a call from participants from related parties. Teaching is an academic activity in the form of communication interactions between teacher and students. Through this interaction, the teacher can activate the student learning process by using a variety of learning methods, so that learning can become more attractive to students. To achieve effective and meaningful interactions, teacher potential needs to be increased. Teacher potential development can be done through development programs that are tailored to the needs of teachers. Efforts that can be made by school principals to improve the ability of teachers include: (a) Providing opportunities to attend education and training; (b) Sending teachers to attend training or training, and (c) Facilitating activities teacher organization.

Implementation of teachers' professionalism capability improvement as the results of the study showed that the implementation of the teacher professional capacity improvement program had been carried out according to plan. However, there are still obstacles, both obstacles originating from school institutions, from teachers and from related agencies, which can hamper the effectiveness of these activities. Among the obstacles faced in implementing this program are funding, lack of socialization from the education ministry, teachers not teaching in their area of expertise, some teachers lack technology, lack of school infrastructure, the low willingness of teachers to develop themselves, and the lack of school supervisors who understand the vocational high school curriculum. Obstacles are inseparable aspects of an activity. Being aware of this, the steps that schools can take regarding funding issues is to submit budgeting according to the needs of the school in a certain amount and period to the education office. Furthermore, the school's need for adequate infrastructure can support the learning process. Provision of educational facilities and infrastructure is the responsibility of local governments. Educational facilities such as educational equipment, learning media, books and learning resources, consumables, and other equipment needed to support learning. Educational infrastructure includes classrooms, headmaster's room, teacher's room, administration room, library room, laboratory, workshop room, production unit

room, canteen, sports field, place of worship, and other spaces needed at school. The need for teachers is also important because teachers are the spearhead of the meaningfulness and success of education. Schools need teachers who teach according to their field of science. But in vocational high schools, there are still teachers who teach not following their educational qualifications. Furthermore, vocational high schools need school supervisors who truly understand the vocational high school curriculum and have the ability to assist teachers to solve problems encountered in implementing learning.

5. Conclusions and Suggestions

The teacher professional capacity building program is carried out following the needs of the teacher which is prepared each year by involving the school principal, vice principals, and chairpersons majors/study programs, school supervisors, teacher organization forums, and senior teachers. The program contains efforts to develop teacher competencies that will be implemented in schools and outside schools. Teacher professionalism has been done at school and outside of school. Teachers who have participated in development/training activities should socialize the knowledge they have gained to other teachers, but have not yet run optimally. Constraints faced in the implementation of increasing the professional abilities of teachers include funding, lack of socialization from the education office, the field of science teachers is not in accordance with educational qualifications, there are still teachers who have not mastered the science of technology, and infrastructure is also an obstacle that is still faced by schools.

Vocational teacher professional development programs that have been prepared should be reformulated by involving school principals, supervisors, vice principals, school teacher organization forums and teachers to be trained/developed. Because if it involves the people who will be involved in its implementation, it will be easier to choose development techniques if the problems faced by the teachers in learning are known first. The implementation of improving the professional abilities of teachers must be done by the aim to improve learning. Training activities need to be further improved and need to be socialized back to the training site, especially training outside of school, so that the material delivered is by the development and changes in the vocational high school curriculum. All obstacles encountered can be overcome if involved by everyone involved in this activity, namely the trainer and the parties being trained. Development should prioritize togetherness, mutual need, mutual sharing so that a harmonious relationship can be created, and the goals to be achieved can be achieved with maximum impact on improving the quality of education in the future.

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*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: tyasyes@ gmail.com/lamhot.naibaho@ uki.ac.id